

Examples of the Method of Deductive Inference of Consequences with the Scheme Construction Implements

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Abstract. This paper contains examples of the implementation of the method of deductive inference of consequences with the construction of the scheme and the auxiliary procedure used in it.

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1 Introduction

The paper discusses in detail two examples.

- Example of implements of disjuncts division procedure using the formulation of the classical problem of an escort.
- Example of implements of consequences inference method using the formulation of the classical problem of an filiation.

2 Example of Complete Division of Disjuncts Procedure Implementation

The initial data are the following disjuncts.

1. likes(Jill,wine): $1 \rightarrow P(a, c)$ or $1 \rightarrow P(a, c)[1, +]$;
2. likes(John,food): $1 \rightarrow P(b, e)$ or $1 \rightarrow P(b, e)[2, +]$;
3. likes(John,wine): $1 \rightarrow P(b, c)$ or $1 \rightarrow P(b, c)[3, +]$;
4. likes(y , wine) & male(x) \rightarrow escort(x, y): $P(y, c) \wedge P_1(x) \rightarrow R(x, y)$ or $1 \rightarrow P(y, c)[+, 4] \vee P_1(x)[+, 4] \vee R(x, y)[4, +]$;
5. New fact: male(John): $1 \rightarrow P_1(b)$ or $1 \rightarrow P_1(b)[5, +]$.

In procedure $\Omega = \langle D, d, m^F, c, Q, S, G \rangle$ of complete division of disjuncts the disjunct of premise (4): $D = P(y, c)[+, 4] \vee P_1(x)[+, 4] \vee R(x, y)[4, +]$ will appear as disjunct-dividend D , and the new fact (5): $d = P_1(b)[5, +]$ will appear as disjunct-divisor. $M^F = \{P(a, c)[1, +], P(b, e)[2, +], P(b, c)[3, +]\}$, $c = \emptyset$.

1. Preparatory step. For the pair $\langle b, d \rangle$, $b = P(y, c)[+, 4] \vee P_1(x)[+, 4] \vee R(x, y)[4, +]$, $d = P_1(b)[5, +]$, ω -procedure is performed. The matrix of "derivatives" is calculated:

$$P_1(b)[5, +] \begin{pmatrix} P(y, c)[+, 4] & P_1(x)[+, 4] & R(x, y)[4, +] \\ 1 & \Delta_{12} & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

In the matrix "derivatives" $\Delta_{11} = \Delta_{13} = 1$, and "derivative" Δ_{12} is determined with the help of unifying substitution $\lambda_{12} = b/x$: $\Delta_{12} = P(y, c)[+, 4] \vee R(b, y)[4, +] = b_1$. Remainder b_1 not equal to one is obtained, that is why it is accepted that $q = 0$ and the initial data for the main step are formed: $n = \langle b_1, d_1, g_1 \rangle$. Disjunct d_t is formed by complementing disjunct d_{*t} with literals of the set of input data M^F , the set of new facts m^F and the set of previously obtained consequences c . In this case disjunct d_{*1} is obtained from disjunct d as a result of excluding the literal, to which the matrix-line, containing only one not equal to one "derivative", presenting remainder b_1 , corresponds. Thus, we obtain: $d_{*1} = 0$, and $d_1 = P(a, c)[1, +] \vee P(b, e)[2, +] \vee P(b, c)[3, +]$. As there are no "derivative" one-literal remainders with predicates without inversions in the matrix, then $s = \emptyset$, but $g_1 = \{P_1(b)[5, \{b/x\}4]\}$.

2. The main step (first implementation, $h = 0, S_0 = s = \emptyset, G_0 = g' = \emptyset$). For three remainders $\langle b_1, d_1, g_1 \rangle$, where $b_1 = P(y, c)[+, 4] \vee R(b, y)[4, +]$, $d_1 = P(a, c)[1, +] \vee P(b, e)[2, +] \vee P(b, c)[3, +]$, $g_1 = \{P_1(b)[5, \{b/x\}4]\}$ ω -procedure is performed:

$$\begin{matrix} & P(y, c)[+, 4] & R(b, y)[4, +] \\ P(a, c)[1, +] & \left(\begin{matrix} \Delta_{11} & 1 \\ 1 & 1 \\ \Delta_{31} & 1 \end{matrix} \right) \\ P(b, e)[2, +] & & \\ P(b, c)[3, +] & & \end{matrix}$$

In the matrix "derivatives" $\Delta_{12} = \Delta_{21} = \Delta_{22} = \Delta_{32} = 1$. And two "derivatives" are different from one: $\Delta_{11} = R(b, a)[4, +]$ if $\lambda_{11} = \{a/y\}$ and $\Delta_{31} = R(b, b)[4, +]$ if $\lambda_{31} = \{b/y\}$. Thus, we obtained "derivatives", presenting consequences, that is why these predicates are included in set of consequences $s = \{R(b, a)[\{a/y, b/x\}4, +], R(b, b)[\{b/y, b/x\}4, +]\}$, $g' = \{\{P_1(b)[5, \{b/x\}4], P(a, c)[1, \{a/y\}4]\}$, $\{P_1(b)[5, \{b/x\}4], P(b, c)[3, \{b/y\}4]\}$.

The set of consequences is complemented: $S_1 = S_0 \cup s = \{R(b, a)[\{a/y, b/x\}4, +], R(b, b)[\{b/y, b/x\}4, +]\}$ and the set of sets of literals of the description of the inference scheme $G_1 = G_0 \cup g' = \{\{P_1(b)[5, \{b/x\}4], P(a, c)[1, \{a/y\}4]\}$, $\{P_1(b)[5, \{b/x\}4], P(b, c)[3, \{b/y\}4]\}$. As $S_1 \neq \emptyset$, it is determined that $Q_1 = 0$. Partial attribute of the solution q_1 is analyzed. There are no remainders, containing more than one literal in the matrix of "derivatives", that is why it is accepted that $q_1 = 1, Q = Q_1, S = S_1, G = G_1$ and point 3 is performed.

3. Final step. The results of the calculation of procedure Ω are recorded: the attribute of solution $Q = 0$, the set of consequences $S = \{R(b, a)[\{a/y, b/x\}4, +], R(b, b)[\{b/y, b/x\}4, +]\}$ and the set of sets of literals of the description of inference scheme $G = \{\{P_1(b)[5, \{b/x\}4], P(a, c)[1, \{a/y\}4]\}$, $\{P_1(b)[5, \{b/x\}4], P(b, c)[3, \{b/y\}4]\}$.

The consequences obtained mean, that from the new fact male (John) basing on the initial data (1 — 4) it is inferred that John is Jill's escort, and also the escort of "himself".

3 Example of the Method of Inference of Consequences Implements

Let us illustrate the usage of the method of inference of consequences by the example about filiation from the work [1]. The initial data are the following disjuncts.

Father (F) is a male person (Per), being a parent (P). Grandfather (GF) is the father of the parent. Brothers or sisters (S) are two different (N) persons, having a common parent. Aunt (A) is a person, who is a sister of the parent. We know that Dimitry (a) is the parent of Victoria (b), Vladimir (c) is the parent of Natalia (d), Dimitry is a male (m), Victoria is a female (f). New facts consist in Vladimir being the child of Dimitry, and Vladimir and Victoria being different people.

A formal presentation of the task looks as follows.

1. $F(x, y)[1, +] \vee Per(x, m)[+, 1] \vee P(x, y)[+, 1]$;
2. $GF(x, y)[2, +] \vee F(x, z)[+, 2] \vee P(z, y)[+, 2]$;
3. $S(x, y)[3, +] \vee P(z, x)[+, 3] \vee P(z, y)[+, 3] \vee N(x, y)[+, 3]$;
4. $A(x, y)[4, +] \vee Per(x, f)[+, 4] \vee P(z, y)[+, 4] \vee S(x, z)[+, 4]$;
5. $P(a, b)[5, +]$;
6. $P(c, d)[6, +]$;
7. $Per(a, m)[7, +]$;
8. $Per(b, f)[8, +]$;
9. New facts: $P(a, c)[9, +], N(b, c)[9, +]$.

Logical inference will consist of the following steps.

Determination of the initial values: $h = 1, M = \{D_1, D_2, D_3, D_4, D_5, D_6\}$ ($M^F = \{D_5, D_6\}$), $m^F = \{P(a, c)[9, +], N(b, c)[9, +]\}$. Forming the inferred disjunct $R_1 = P(a, c)[9, +] \vee N(b, c)[9, +]$, consisting of literals, forming set m^F . Determining set of consequences e_0 , coinciding with facts M^F , contained in the premise: $e_0 = M^F \cap m^F = \emptyset, s^0 = \{e_0\}, c_1 = e_0 = \emptyset$. Determining the initial value of the general attribute of the continuation of inference: $P_0 = 0$. The results of the procedure of inference are presented in the figure 1

The general set of consequences is obtained by means of joining sets of the set of sets s^3 : $MS = \{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1, +], S(b, c)[\{a/z, b/x, c/y\}3, +], GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2, +], A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4, +]\}$. The description of the inference scheme is presented like $O = \{\{P(a, c)[9, \{a/x, c/y\}1], Per(a, m)[7, 1], N(b, c)[9, \{b/x, c/y\}3], P(a, c)[9, \{a/z\}3], P(a, b)[5, 3]\}, \{F(a, c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1, \{a/x, c/z\}2], P(c, d)[6, \{d/y\}2], S(b, c)[\{a/z, b/x, c/y\}3, \{b/x, c/z\}4], P(c, d)[6, \{d/y\}4], Per(b, f)[8, 4]\}, \{GF(a, d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2, +], A(b, d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4, +]\}$.

The graphic presentation of the inference scheme is shown in the figure 2.

The dividend	The attribute of the solution	The set of consequences and the set of sets of literals of the description of the inference scheme	The attribute of the continuation of inference	The set of sets of consequences and the description of the inference scheme	The general attribute of the continuation of inference
Procedure of inference v_1 ($R_1 = P(a,c)[9,+] \vee N(b,c)[9,+]$)					
D_1	$Q_1 = 0$	$S_1 = \{F(a,c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1,+],$ $G_1 = \{\{P(a,c)[9,\{a/x, c/y\}1],$ $Per(a,m)[7,1]\}\}$	$p_1 = 0$	$s^1 = \{\{F(a,c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1,+],$ $S(b,c)[\{a/z, b/x, c/y\}3,+]\},$ $O = \{\{P(a,c)[9,\{a/x, c/y\}1],$ $Per(a,m)[7,1], N(b,c)[9,\{b/x, c/y\}3],$ $P(a,c)[9,\{a/z\}3],$ $P(a,b)[5,3]\}\}$	$P_1 = 0$
D_2	$Q_2 = 1$	$S_2 = \emptyset$			
D_3	$Q_3 = 0$	$S_3 = \{S(b,c)[\{a/z, b/x, c/y\}3,+],$ $G_3 = \{\{N(b,c)[9,\{b/x, c/y\}3],$ $P(a,c)[9,\{a/z\}3],$ $P(a,b)[5,3]\}\}$			
D_4	$Q_4 = 1$	$S_4 = \emptyset$			
Procedure of inference v_2 ($R_2 = F(a,c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1,+] \vee S(b,c)[\{a/z, b/x, c/y\}3,+]$)					
D_1	$Q_1 = 0$	$S_1 = \{GF(a,d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2,+],$ $G_1 = \{\{F(a,c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1, \{a/x, c/z\}2],$ $P(c,d)[6,\{d/y\}2]\}\}$	$p_2 = 0$	$s^2 = \{\{F(a,c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1,+],$ $S(b,c)[\{a/z, b/x, c/y\}3,+]\},$ $\{GF(a,d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2,+],$ $A(b,d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4,+]\},$ $O = \{\{P(a,c)[9,\{a/x, c/y\}1],$ $Per(a,m)[7,1], N(b,c)[9,\{b/x, c/y\}3],$ $P(a,c)[9,\{a/z\}3],$ $P(a,b)[5,3]\},$ $\{F(a,c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1, \{a/x, c/z\}2],$ $P(c,d)[6,\{d/y\}2],$ $S(b,c)[\{a/z, b/x, c/y\}3, \{b/x, c/z\}4],$ $P(c,d)[6,\{d/y\}4],$ $Per(b,f)[8,4]\}\}$	$P_2 = 0$
D_4	$Q_4 = 0$	$S_4 = \{A(b,d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4,+],$ $G_4 = \{\{S(b,c)[\{a/z, b/x, c/y\}3, \{b/x, c/z\}4],$ $P(c,d)[6,\{d/y\}4],$ $Per(b,f)[8,4]\}\}$			
Procedure of inference v_3 ($R_3 = GF(a,d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2,+] \vee A(b,d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4,+]$)					
<i>None of the rules is divided by the inferred disjunct</i>			$p_3 = 0$	$s^3 = \{\{F(a,c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1,+],$ $S(b,c)[\{a/z, b/x, c/y\}3,+]\},$ $\{GF(a,d)[\{a/x, c/z, d/y\}2,+],$ $A(b,d)[\{b/x, c/z, d/y\}4,+]\},$ $O = \{\{P(a,c)[9,\{a/x, c/y\}1],$ $Per(a,m)[7,1], N(b,c)[9,\{b/x, c/y\}3],$ $P(a,c)[9,\{a/z\}3],$ $P(a,b)[5,3]\},$ $\{F(a,c)[\{a/x, c/y\}1, \{a/x, c/z\}2],$ $P(c,d)[6,\{d/y\}2],$ $S(b,c)[\{a/z, b/x, c/y\}3, \{b/x, c/z\}4],$ $P(c,d)[6,\{d/y\}4],$ $Per(b,f)[8,4]\}\}$	$P_3 = 1$

Fig. 1. Results of the Procedure of Inference

Thus, in the process of inference of consequences we determined, that Dimitry is Vladimir's father ($F(a, c)$), Vladimir and Victoria are brother and sister ($S(b, c)$), Dimitry has a granddaughter Natalia ($GF(a, d)$), and Natalia has aunt Victoria ($A(b, d)$).

References

1. Ceri, S., Gottlob, G., Tanca, L.: Logic Programming and Databases. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg (1990)

Fig. 2. The Scheme of Inference